

Participant Post-hackathon Interview Guide for Hybrid Hackathons

This post-hackathon interview guide is designed to capture the participant's perception of their experience and perspectives about a hybrid hackathon.

Introduction

"Thank you for participating in this study. The aim is to explore how hybrid hackathons function, identify best practices, and derive suggestions for future event organisers and participants. During the interview, we will discuss your motivations for participation, your experience during the hackathon related to team dynamics, utilization of technology, spatial arrangements, and the projects you worked on. The interviews will be audio-recorded."

Motivation and mode of participation

Let's start by talking about why you decided to participate in this hackathon.

- How did you participate in the hackathon? [*in person, remote*]
- Why did you decide to participate [*in person, remote*]?
- Would you also have participated [*!in person, !remote*]? Why / why not?

Preparation [team formation, idea generation, set-up]

Let's talk about how you prepared for the hackathon

- Were there any specific resources or guidelines provided by the organizers that you found useful for your preparation? [*probe: event agenda, setup software, technology*]
- [*if remote*] How did you prepare your remote setup in advance of the hackathon?
- [*if in-person*] Describe your physical setup for me at the venue [*probe: microphone and camera placement, equipment to show online participants*]

At the beginning of the hackathon [planning, initial communication]

Let's move into the hackathon event day.

- Did you join as an individual or part of a pre-formed team?
 - What was the composition of your team in terms of in-person and online participants? Any timezone differences?
 - [*If part of a pre-formed team*] Did you have any preparatory meetings before the hackathon? What were they focused on? [*probe: team role assignment, technologies/communication protocols, ideation/brainstorming*]

- Where were you located? Where were your team members located?
 - Did you change locations?
- How did you set up your communication within your team?
 - Which technologies - if any - did you use? How did you decide which technologies would be used?
- How did you decide which project to work on? Who was involved in the decision? *[probe: mainly in-person or remote participants?]*

During the hackathon [team collaboration, parallel work, team project]

How were roles distributed among the team?

- Was there a designated leader within your team? *[probe: in-person or remote?]*
 - How was the team leader selected?
 - What were their tasks?
 - How effective was their leadership?
- Were there any other team-related roles or responsibilities taken? *[probe: note taker, time-keeper, presenter]* *[probe: in-person or remote?]*

Can you tell me about how your team collaborated during the hackathon?

- How did your team decide who does what?
- How did you keep track of your own tasks? How did you know what the other participants were doing? How did you know what was still left to do?
- How did you make sure that everyone was aligned and on the same page?
- How active were your other team members? *[probe: in-person or remote?]*
- Were there any parallel activities you were involved in?
 - Were you aware of any parallel activities of your team members? ***[If yes: What were they?]*** *[probe: in-person or remote?]*
- Which technologies did you end up using during the event? *[probe for purposes: manage tasks, communicate, collaborate or work together, or share information]*

How - if at all - did you participate in activities outside of teamwork? *[probe: games, networking, breaks]*

At the end of the hackathon [end of event, contribution]

Let's talk about the end of the hackathon. How did your team put everything together?

- How did everyone contribute to the project?
 - Did everyone contribute equally? *[if not, probe for specifics]*
 - ***[if remote]*** Did being remote affect your ability to contribute? How so?

- Looking back, how many of your ideas and contributions ended up in the project?
Can you give me some concrete examples?

After the hackathon [project outcome, reflection]

Reflecting on your hackathon experience, I'm interested in your perspectives on the team dynamics and the event's organization.

- Did your team see any changes in the mode of attendance (from online to in-person or vice versa)? [*probe*]
 - *When and why did this happen?*
 - *[if so] how did this impact your team's collaboration?*
- Was the venue equipped to support both in-person and online participants adequately?
 - If not, what were the limitations?
 - What something missing?
- How did the organization of the event affect your collaboration (e.g. checkpoints, games, food, etc.)?

Hackathon outcome and closing

Now that the hackathon has concluded let's discuss your overall experience and your thoughts on the hybrid format.

- Are you satisfied with the outcome of your project?
 - Did the hybrid format impact your project outcome in any way?
- Are you satisfied with the way your team worked together?
- What did you think worked well in the hybrid format? What would you change?
- Will you participate in future hybrid hackathons? [*probe: why? why not?*]
- Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience?